

2026 Brian Kaess Family Annual Message

Hello,

June 9, 2026

Greetings from Mexico! We hope this message finds everyone in good health and prosperity. Mayte has been busy selling houses and I am hopeful this may be the year I finally buy a cell phone- that's right I'm one of those old-timers that just used email for awhile. Without a cell phone, I'm starting to feel like a Mennonite! Paul spent some time with us in Durango after working in Chicago. He managed to help me with some family photos I dug out of the storage room boxes. He has since left for Puebla and is eagerly looking for work there while he seeks some side jobs and film projects. We are hoping to witness a certain *profusion* in his creativity as he develops films. He hasn't made too many *perturbations* to his plans. Follow your dreams!

Garret will visit us with Kathy in June and he sent photos from his trip to Iceland, that land *juxtaposed* with fire and ice. May his further travels ride on the 'wings of God's blessings.' He doesn't exactly bear the *stamp* of poverty anymore. Garret just 'keeps on travelin' as Rick Steves would say.

By the star when it sets! We support President Trump's *Operation Epic Fury* and our U.S. military personnel. We hope that fortune opens her gates to his plans of peace and reconstruction. So, let us not be chary to blaze a new path.

The USA nabbing of Maduro was 'cleaner' than I expected- worries of a prolonged ground war were a concern. I am happy that Delcy Rodrigues has decided to work with the USA and allow us to extract oil and minerals, not only for USA benefit, but for the improvement of the lot of ordinary Venezuelans. Maybe they will allow Christian groups to send in food aid to both Venezuela and Iran someday. Maybe Cuba is next too? We also pray for the improvement of food insecurity in the USA. Don't forget- we're not Christian because of how we are born, but because of how we are born again!

I support continued USA economic and military aid to Isreal. The Gaza Riviera sounds like a great idea. Humanitarian aid is the way to go once tensions settle down and the kettle is no longer hot!

I also support Pres. Zelensky and the Ukrainian people in their *Revanchist* strategy and oppose Russian *Irredentism*. I praise Ukraine's use of drone technology and hope attrition doesn't whittle away their victory. Putin has still yet to distill a compelling message why this war began in the first place! We pray Ukrainian culture is not extinguished in these flames of war. As the Poet once wrote: 'Alas for those days of yore, when Nature lay vassal to pagan lore!' I still support *American Veterans for Ukraine*. Slava Ukrayini!

Our cats Candy, Nieve & Sabrina are doing great and getting plenty of food, water and TLC. Boy, do they love those Ham slices on payday!

So, we pray for Peace in the World and Goodwill among mankind!

God Bless Everyone and God Bless America! MIGA!

Brian & Family